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Principals' Funds Management Strategies As Predictors Of Effective Secondary School Administration In Cross River State Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Education is the most crucial aspect of a country's development and has existed for as long as humans. The study examined how principals' funds management strategies predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State. Three objectives, research questions and hypotheses respectively were formulated to guide the study. A correlational survey design was adopted. The Population of the study consisted of all the 291 principals and 582 vice principals in 291 public secondary schools in Cross Rivers State. The sample of this study comprised 146 principals and 291 vice principals of public secondary schools in Cross Rivers State, representing 50% of 291 and 582 public secondary school principals and vice principals respectively. The instruments used for data collection were questionnaires titled: "Effective Secondary School Administration Questionnaire (ESSAQ)" and the "Principals Funds Management Strategies Questionnaire (PFMSQ)". Simple Regression was used in answering the research questions, while t-test statistics associated with simple regression analysis at 0.05 level of significance was used in testing hypotheses. The findings revealed that, principals' budgeting role, book keeping and regular auditing significantly predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State. The study concluded that precise documentation promotes responsibility, openness, and effective use of resources—all of which are essential for accomplishing learning objectives. Regular auditing is also essential for encouraging accountability, openness, and effectiveness in school management.

Keywords: Funds, Management, Budgeting, Book Keeping, Auditing, Principals

INTRODUCTION

Education is the most crucial aspect of a country's development and has existed for as long as humans. The education system in every nation is a vital tool for socioeconomic advancement; without it, neither a nation nor an individual may experience economic and professional growth (Ololube, Ololube & Aiya, 2016a; Ololube, Onyekwere & Agbor, 2016b). Therefore, it is expected that the funds provided to the educational system will be administered appropriately. In the beginning, missions that introduced and constructed schools in Nigeria were in charge of providing funding for them.

However, any educational sector's ability to expand and thrive depends entirely on how well its funds are managed. Since education is the primary tool for a country's sustainable growth, it is a costly social service provided by the government to its residents. Any organization's ability to finance the creation,

management, and upkeep of established standards is heavily reliant on its financial resources (Adewale & Zubaedy, 2019; Nungu *et al.*, 2023). As a result, secondary school principals are the key component upon which school organization is based. In order to prevent financial mismanagement, this institution needs to have an effective financial management system; in contrast, if the principal is weak and ineffective in managing the school's resources, success would be extremely difficult to achieve (Agyemang *et al.*, 2018; Mayevskaya, 2018; Riddell, 2015). As a result, fund management by the school administrator needs a managerial function that deals with the planning, acquisition, and distribution of financial resources to meet predetermined goals in public secondary schools.

Nonetheless, poor student performance may result from principals' carelessness and mishandling of school funding, which could delay the purchase of necessary teaching and learning resources. Previous research confirmed that because of the high level of corruption in many countries around the world, financial mismanagement may not be the result of carelessness or errors but rather of deliberate misappropriation (Osuji & Nyebuchi, 2021). For efficient school administration, it is therefore essential that principals possess decision-making expertise. As secondary school top executives, principals should be able to make wise judgments that will meet the demands of the school and its employees in general (Olaifa *et al.*, 2024).

Drafting a budget, which outlines the school's financial statement in monetary terms, is typically the first step in the planning of school finances. According to a previous study, budgeting is a method that school administrators use to help decide how much money will be needed and how it will be spent (Ugwu *et al.*, 2020). According to earlier research, the educational budget is a document that outlines the financing of the many educational programs planned for the year or another specified term (Kwaghbo, 2022). According to other research highlighting the significance of school budgeting, a management plan like a school budget helps to identify numerous issues before they arise and avoid resource waste (Omosidi *et al.*, 2019). By connecting resource application to planned programs, it also makes the procedures of delegation, control, evaluation, and accountability easier (Olaifa *et al.*, 2024). In other words, the main goal of budget administration is to ensure that the school's accomplishments carefully justify the expenditure.

Budgeting, according to earlier research, ensures that only planned programs are pursued, unnecessary spending is avoided, and all proposed expenditures are matched to the expected revenue, leaving no room for a deficit but instead increasing the amount of money available for surplus (Sambo & Imiete, 2018). This ensures that school administration is effective. A method that is founded on reliable and high-quality data must result in a successful school budget.

According to another study, school budgets project the programs, services, and activities that have been approved by the relevant governing council (such as the board of governors) for a specific time frame, often one year, regarding revenue and expenses (Ogbonnaya, 2012). The budget for the school outlines the expected revenue and the source of that revenue. The school budget provides information, a statement, and an estimate of how much each item in the entire school system will cost (Olaifa *et al.*, 2024).

One of the key tools for resolving financial issues is record keeping. It is stipulated that accurate record keeping is necessary for efficient planning and management of funds in schools (Arhipova *et al.*, 2021; Titus & Ukaigwe, 2018), that all financial transactions must be kept securely in a record book, and that accounting is a crucial component of managing the school's finances (Arhipova *et al.*, 2021; Titus & Ukaigwe, 2018). The principal is responsible and accountable for the financial management of all the money that the school collects and disbursements (Osuji & Nyebuchi, 2021). The principal must support the execution of its statutory functions pertaining to assets, liabilities, property, and other financial management issues.

According to a previous study, school records are records of information (data) on the facilities and human resources that a school has (Odeniyi & Adeyanju, 2020). A document or description of events or activities involving people and facilities in the school that may be used as a future reference is known as a school record. In the educational system, maintaining records is essential; without it, accountability would not exist. To give a proper account, the head of the school who handles a lot of money throughout the

year needs to maintain a tight record of the cash book (Boma, 2018; Zhang *et al.*, 2020). Prior research highlighted the significance of maintaining accurate financial records and tasked school administrators, who oversee accounting, with doing so (Ezeh & Ogara, 2021). This is due to the fact that finding errors, losses, and financial mismanagement requires reliable records and regular checks. According to Pius-Uwhubetiyi (2020), another study found three fundamental stages of record keeping that are applicable to all organizations..

According to research, thorough budgeting and financial planning are the first steps towards effective money management (Ironkwe *et al.*, 2024). Principals are in charge of estimating revenue and expenses, drafting thorough budgets, and making sure money is distributed sensibly to support educational requirements. According to a study conducted in Anambra State, better administrative effectiveness is closely connected with sound financial planning techniques, such as following budgeting plans. However, frequent spending monitoring guarantees that money is spent wisely and in line with the objectives of the organization (Ironkwe *et al.*, 2024).

Over time, Cross River State principals' fund management procedures have grown to be a delicate subject. This is a result of the public's and the government's rising interest in and concern about funding school program implementation. The public expects administrators to make sure school finances are managed responsibly. Principals are being subjected to a flurry of rumors and accusations regarding financial mismanagement, neglect of budgetary plans for funding school programs, poor fund distribution, a shortage of trained staff like cashiers and bursars, some principals' lack of financial management training, the imposition of unlawful levies on students, the failure to complete government-approved and funded projects, poor record keeping, misuse of PTA funds, etc. (Amirize & Ololube, 2018).

Rationale for the Study

Financial issues including bad administration and the nation's economic downturn may be blamed for the subpar secondary school atmosphere. In Cross River State, one of the biggest barriers to the efficient operation of secondary schools is poor financial management. Many school administrators struggle to develop and implement school budgets that align with the school's goals, which is typically the root of the issue. The state of secondary schools has deteriorated to the point where, in spite of all the federal government's financial contributions and other funding sources available to schools, teaching and learning have gotten little attention.

The government claims that it is making every effort to ensure that the school has enough funding to operate properly, but the administrators are not managing these monies well enough in terms of accountability, budgeting, or record-keeping. Principals contend that the government does not provide the real funding required for secondary schools to be run efficiently. One factor contributing to the concern about a declining quality of education in Cross River State is the improper handling of fees and funds intended for the children's education. Unfortunately, some principals and financial clerks embezzle the government-paid allocations that are intended to support their students' welfare and school maintenance. Therefore, the researcher is interested in advancing further on this subject by examining how principals' budgetary role, book keeping and auditing can predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State.

Purpose of the Study

This study is aimed at investigating how Principals funds management strategies predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State. To further address this, the study was broken down to specific objectives, which includes;

1. Ascertain the extent to which principals' budgeting roles predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State.
2. Examine the extent to which principals' book keeping predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State.
3. Find out the extent to which regular auditing predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were formulated to guide the study;

- To what extent does principals' budgeting role predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State?
- To what extent does principals' book keeping predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State?
- To what extent does regular auditing predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State?

Hypotheses

1. Principals' budgeting role does not significantly predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State.
2. Principals' book keeping does not significantly predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State.
3. Regular auditing does not significantly predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State.

Theoretical Framework

Accountability Theory

This theory was proposed by Lerner and Tetlock (1999). According to accountability theory, one becomes reflective and feels responsible for the methods used to obtain decisions and judgments because of the seeming necessity to hide one's activities from another party. According to Tetlock and Lenner (1999), the probability that someone will reason deeply and methodically about their everyday ways increases as a result of this seeming necessity to account for a decision-making process and outcome.

The former also suggests that understanding answerability by differentiating between its two most common uses as a mechanism and a virtue is a valuable approach. Liability is viewed as a positive attribute that demonstrates a willingness to take responsibility, which is a desirable quality in public officials, government organizations, or businesses; as such, it is a useful characteristic of an entity. As a piece of machinery, it is viewed as a procedure wherein an individual makes a possible promise to explain their activities to a third party who has the authority to judge them and to ask them about any hidden consequences of their behavior. Recent studies have demonstrated that the four main tenets of accountability theory—identifiability, the expectation of evaluation, awareness of monitoring, and social presence—can be impacted by information technology design artifacts of systems. Without requiring training or disruptive interventions, this increases employee accountability for organizational system security (Trevor, Anderson & Didier, 2016).

Accountability theory is pertinent to this research since it will help determine how principals' budget management techniques might forecast successful secondary school management. There will be a high degree of accountability regarding potential financial management strategies if principals and teachers embrace the virtue of thinking deeply and methodically about their actions, which is increased when one feels compelled to account for a decision-making process and outcome. Due to the expectation of evaluation, monitoring awareness, and social presence through efficient school administration, principals and teachers are aware that the education board will use external auditing to confirm their financial statements and provide audit reports, which may not be taken lightly if they fail to be accountable. Transparency is improved and fraud is decreased because other stakeholders are engaged in keeping an eye on financial accountability.

Empirical Reviews

Olaifa et al. (2024) examined the connection between the efficacy of school administration and the fund management tactics used by principals. It evaluated the perceived level of administrative effectiveness, the budgeting practices of administrators, and the impact of fund management on the efficacy of secondary schools.. The sort of research design used was a descriptive survey. In this survey, all 132

secondary schools were included in the population. Forty (40) principals, or 30% of the total number of respondents, were chosen through the use of the stratified random sampling technique.

Data was gathered using a self-created survey called the "Principals' Fund Management Strategies and School Administrative Effectiveness in Secondary Schools Questionnaire (PFMSSAEQ)". A reliability coefficient of 0.76 was obtained using Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (r). The findings demonstrated that principals maintained precise spending logs, were mediocreatively effective, and significantly impacted secondary school money management. Given its importance in efficient secondary school financial administration, it was suggested that the Ministry of Education closely supervise principals to make sure they continue to preserve accurate records. The present study investigated principal's budgeting, book keeping and auditing as funds management strategies for maintaining effective administration of schools, which a departure from the previous studies.

Fund management techniques for the efficient operation of public secondary schools in Rivers State were examined by Amirize and Ololube (2018). The study used a descriptive survey to gather opinions from Rivers State secondary school principals on the function of fund management strategies, accountability, and the elements that support and undermine efficient secondary school administration. Because they are principals who would respond to the questions posed by their roles as principals in the selected local government districts, purposeful sampling was employed. The instrument, called the Fund Management Strategies for Effective Administration of Public Secondary Schools Questionnaire (FMSEAPSSQ), was a 26-item survey. According to the study, there are important connections between the fund management tactics used by principals, accountability, and the elements that support and undermine efficient secondary school administration in Rivers State.

In the Calabar Education Zone of Cross River State, Nigeria, Eni, Olowonefa, and Etta (2021) investigated the impact of financial management on the work performance of school principals. The study specifically evaluated how principals' job performance was impacted by budget creation, budget reviews, macroeconomic variables, deficit account balances, accounting records, cash usage prior to banking, and fraudulent activities. The study design used was correlational. A systematic questionnaire called the "Financial Management and School Principals' Job Performance Questionnaire (FMSPJPQ)" was used to gather data from 200 respondents.

Based on the study's findings, principals' work performance in the Calabar Education Zone is negatively and negligibly impacted by macroeconomic conditions, cash consumption prior to banking, and deficit account balance. Furthermore, it was demonstrated that budget reviews, accounting records and fraudulent activities all significantly and favorably impact principals' job performance. Results also showed that budget creation has a major negative impact on job performance. The study came to the conclusion that school principals' job performance is significantly impacted by financial management based on these data. In order to improve their job performance, it was suggested, among other things, that principals devote sufficient resources to learning and gaining financial management skills and approaches.

In order to administer public secondary schools in Rivers State effectively, Amadi, Barango-Tariah, Barieere, and Awala (2023) looked at the financial management techniques used by principals. The research design used for this study was a descriptive survey. Purposive and cluster random sampling techniques were employed in the multistage sampling approach to establish the sample size of 344. Data was gathered using a self-structured study tool called the "Financial Management Practices by Principals for Effective Administration Questionnaire." The study's conclusions showed that although principals in public secondary schools in Rivers State implemented financial management procedures, teachers and other staff did not participate in budget preparation, there was a clear lack of technical expertise in financial concepts, and principals continued to deny independent operations to internal auditors. Therefore, it was suggested that the Ministry of Education and Senior Secondary Schools Board host seminars, conferences, and workshops for principals and school bursars to improve their knowledge of financial management techniques.

Ondieki (2015) looked into the variables influencing the financial management of public secondary schools in Kenya's Marani Sub-County and found that most of them had debts and financial difficulties before the end of each term. He stated that while the school principals have strong financial management abilities, the majority of the bursars who oversaw school finances lacked these abilities. The research also bemoaned the fact that principals handled school budgets and finances alone in practically every school, with no input from parents, teachers, or students.

According to Ondieki (2015), this circumstance greatly increases the likelihood of embezzlement and misappropriation of school funds because the monitoring and evaluation officer will be the same principal who creates and executes the budget. Additionally, he claimed that this makes it easier to tamper with the books of accounts to the principals' advantage. However, he believed that because most principals lack technical expertise, most of their budgets are incomplete, which makes it difficult to implement the budgets when the actual execution of planned projects begins. This, in turn, results in poor performance of school projects or a number of incomplete projects that are typically seen in such schools.

There is a significant relationship between the availability of school finance management structure and the effective delivery of 21st century secondary education in Cross River State, according to a 2019 study by Ekaette, Akeke, and Ekpenyong. The study also found that secondary schools in the State have access to sufficient funding sources, but there are no formal structures for accountability or the allocation of funds, and the quality of 21st century education in secondary schools is low. This demonstrates how the principals are successfully completing the budget preparation process, despite their weak cash control methods.

Ejoh and Ejom (2014) aimed to ascertain the effect that the internal audit function has on Nigerian tertiary institutions' financial performance. To ascertain the connection between the internal audit function and financial performance in Nigerian tertiary institutions, Cross River State College of Education was utilized as a case study. According to the survey, the top management was primarily in charge of all initiatives started at the college. The investigation found that Cross River College's internal audit division lacked independence and had a small workforce. This suggests that their lack of effectiveness was caused by understaffing and college administrative control. The college's audit model had many problems. The college's financial performance was not significantly impacted by the internal audit function. Given these factors, the report suggested that if the college wants the audit unit to fulfill its duty successfully and efficiently, it should hire enough professionals with the necessary skills. The audit department should also be led by someone with the necessary training and expertise.

Husein (2013) conducted a study on internal auditing practices and the internal control system in Somali remittance firms. Among the auditing practices he identified were reviewing the segregation of duties, testing the procedures for cash receipt and disbursement, checking the accuracy of bank reconciliation, reviewing cash records and tracking down unusual records, testing compliance with credit management procedures, and verifying compliance with established policies and accounting procedures. Given this context, Okeke and Okaforcha (2020) argued that auditing procedures aid in reviewing different school accounting records, determining the extent of compliance with budgetary regulations, and determining the integrity of the school's key financial managers through cash surveys. Additionally, examining school cash books, revenue collected, and fund expansion aids in identifying frauds, errors, and mistakes for potential corrective measures.

RESEARCH METHODS

The research design used in this study was a correlational survey. 291 principals and 582 vice principals from 291 public secondary schools in Nigeria's Cross Rivers State made up the study's population. A stratified selection strategy was utilized in selecting a sample of 146 principals and 291 vice principals of public secondary schools in Cross Rivers State, representing 50% of 291 and 582 public secondary school principals and vice principals respectively in Cross Rivers State, Nigeria. Based on accessibility, the researcher used 291 vice principals and 146 principals, which is a total of 437 respondents. Information for the study was gathered using a 15-item self-designed questionnaire called the "Effective Secondary

School Administration Questionnaire (ESSAQ)" and the "Principals Funds Management Strategies Questionnaire (PFMSQ)."

Sections A and B make up PFMSQ and ESSAQ. Simple questions about demographics were included in Section A, whereas Section B had 15 questions intended to elicit answers to three research questions. A modified four-point Likert scale was used to categorize responses to each section's items: Very High Extent (4), High Extent (3), Low Extent (2), and Very Low Extent (1). The test-retest method was used to determine the instruments' reliability indices. It produced results of 0.82 and 0.87 respectively, indicating good instrument reliability. SPSS was used to examine the data from the administered instrument.

DATA PRESENTATION

Research Question One: *To what extent does principals' budgeting role predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State?*

Table 1: Simple Regression Analysis on the extent principals' budgeting role predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State

Model	R	R Squared	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.708 ^a	.502	.500	2.54075	.502	437.722	1	435	.000

Table 1 demonstrated that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be 0.708 while the regression squared value was computed to be 0.502. This shows that effective secondary school administration in Cross River State is positively and highly predicted by principals' budgeting role. Judging by the coefficient of determination, it shows that 50.2% change in effective secondary school administration in Cross River State can be predicted by principals' budgeting role, while 49.8% was accounted by other variables not considered in this study.

Research Question Two: *To what extent does principals' book keeping predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State?*

Table 2: Simple Regression Analysis on the extent principals' book keeping predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State

Model	R	R Squared	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.764 ^a	.583	.582	2.32372	.583	608.352	1	435	.000

Table 2 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be 0.764 while the regression squared value was computed to be 0.583. This shows that effective secondary school administration in Cross River State is positively and highly predicted by principals' book keeping. Judging by the coefficient of determination, it shows that 58.3% change in effective secondary school administration in Cross River State can be predicted by principals' book keeping, while 41.7% was accounted by other variables not considered in this study.

Research Question Three: *To what extent does regular auditing predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State?*

Table 3: Simple Regression Analysis on the extent regular auditing predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate	Change Statistics				
					R Square Change	F Change	df1	df2	Sig. F Change
1	.619 ^a	.383	.381	2.82726	.383	269.802	1	435	.000

Table 3 revealed that the regression coefficient R was calculated to be 0.619 while the regression squared value was computed to be 0.383. This shows that effective secondary school administration in Cross River State is positively and highly predicted by regular auditing. Judging by the coefficient of determination, it shows that 38.3% change in effective secondary school administration in Cross River State can be predicted by regular auditing, while 61.7% was accounted by other variables not considered in this study.

Testing of Hypotheses

The null hypotheses formulated for the study were tested using t-test associated with simple regression, which is a relationship.

HO₁: Principals’ budgeting role does not significantly predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State.

Table 4: T-test associated with simple Regression on how principal’s budgeting role predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound
1	(Constant)	5.469	.508		10.770	.000	4.471	6.467
	Budgeting Role	.682	.033	.708	20.922	.000	.618	.746

From table 4, the t-test value 20.922 associated with linear regression was statistically significant at 0.000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, principals’ budgeting role significantly predicts effective secondary school administration in Cross River State.

HO₂: Principals’ book keeping does not significantly predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State.

Table 5: T-test associated with simple Regression on how principals’ book keeping predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error				Beta	Lower Bound
1	(Constant)	5.055	.449		11.259	.000	4.173	5.938
	Book Keeping	.717	.029	.764	24.665	.000	.660	.774

From table 5, the t-test value 24.665 associated with linear regression was statistically significant at 0.000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, principals’ book keeping significantly predicts effective secondary school administration in Cross River State.

HO₃: Regular auditing does not significantly predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State.

Table 6: T-test associated with simple Regression on how regular auditing predict effective secondary school administration in Cross River State

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B	
		B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound
1	(Constant)	7.676	.512		14.997	.000	6.670	8.682
	Regular Auditing	.534	.033	.619	16.426	.000	.470	.598

From table 6, the t-test value 16.426 associated with linear regression was statistically significant at 0.000 when subjected to 0.05 alpha level of significance. By implication, the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, regular auditing significantly predicts effective secondary school administration in Cross River State.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Principals’ Budgeting Role and Effective Secondary School Administration

The study found that the budgeting role of principals significantly predicts effective secondary school administration in Cross River State, accounting for 50.2% of the change in effective secondary school administration, while other variables not included in the study accounted for 49.8%.

Adeyemi and Akanbi (2020) examined the role of principals in budgeting and effective school administration in Nigeria. The study used survey research involving 150 principals across public secondary schools in Ogun State, using structured questionnaires. It was revealed that principals who actively engaged in participatory budgeting achieved better resource allocation and staff motivation, leading to effective school administration. Their research outcome agreed with the findings of the present study. However, the previous studies focused on only resource allocation, neglecting other dimensions of budgeting like expenditure monitoring, which the present study considered.

Okeke and Ugochukwu (2019) examined budgeting practices and their impact on secondary school management. The study used case study design in analyzing budget documents and interviewing 50 principals in Southeast Nigeria. It was revealed that schools with transparent budgeting practices experienced enhanced stakeholder trust, translating to increased cooperation and effective administration. This assertion concurred with the outcome of the present study. However, the previous study did not assess the impact of external financial audits on administration.

Bassey and Etim (2021) investigated financial planning as a predictor of administrative effectiveness in public schools. The study adopted quantitative analysis using regression models to evaluate financial planning and administrative outcomes in 75 secondary schools. The findings revealed that budgeting accuracy was strongly associated with the timely execution of school projects and improved staff retention. This outcome aligns with the findings of the present study. While the previous study focused primarily on urban schools, excluding rural settings, the present study included both rural and urban schools.

Principals' Book Keeping and Effective Secondary School Administration

According to the study, the bookkeeping practices of the principals in Cross River State strongly predict the change in effective secondary school administration, accounting for 58.3% of the variation, while other factors not covered in the study accounted for 41.7%.

The effect of financial record-keeping on the effectiveness of school administration in Lagos State's public secondary schools was investigated by Adetunji and Oladele (2020). Questionnaires were used to gather data from 120 school principals as part of a survey research design. It was discovered that schools with reliable and consistent bookkeeping procedures had easier budgeting, better resource distribution, and fewer financial inconsistencies, all of which contributed to efficient administration. The outcome of this study agrees with finding of the present study.

Similarly, Eze and Ugochukwu (2019) looked into leadership efficacy and bookkeeping procedures in secondary schools in southeast Nigeria. 50 principals were interviewed and documents were analyzed as part of the study's mixed-method procedure. The results demonstrated that good bookkeeping had a favorable correlation with transparency and accountability, which raised stakeholder trust and employee morale. This research concurred with the outcome of the present study.

In order to increase administrative effectiveness in Nigerian schools, Nwachukwu et al. (2018) investigated the function of financial management techniques. A quantitative study using regression analysis of 70 secondary schools' financial records was chosen. According to the results, effective bookkeeping improved principals' capacity to keep an eye on spending, manage debt, and make better administrative decisions. This assertion aligns with the findings of the present study.

Also, Basse and Akpan (2020) looked on the efficiency of administration and the handling of financial records in South-South Nigerian secondary schools. A case study methodology was used, looking at 15 schools through financial audits and interviews. According to the study, schools with thorough financial records had fewer cases of mishandled funds, which increased administrative efficacy overall. This however, agrees with the finding of the current study.

Principals' Regular Auditing and Effective Secondary School Administration

Regular auditing, according to the study, is a significant predictor of effective secondary school administration in Cross River State, explaining 38.2% of the variation in effective secondary school administration. Other factors not covered in the study were responsible for 61.7% of the variation.

The effect of financial auditing procedures on school administration in South-Western Nigeria was investigated by Adegbesan and Akinpelu (2021). One hundred principals were surveyed and interviewed as part of a mixed-method study. The results showed that frequent audits enhanced overall school administration by promoting trust among stakeholders, reducing financial misconduct, and increasing openness. This study agrees with the outcome of the current study.

Similarly, the impact of financial accountability through auditing on administrative effectiveness in secondary schools was examined by Ezeocha et al. (2020). In South-East Nigeria, auditing records and their relationship to academic achievement were quantitatively analyzed. According to the results, principals who carried out routine audits showed improved resource allocation and budgeting, which enhanced student achievement. This study agrees with the findings of the present study.

Further, Oladapo and Fashola (2019) looked into how financial audits could improve the efficacy of school management. A descriptive survey was used to collect information from 85 school administrators. Accordingly, the study found that auditing procedures guaranteed appropriate use of school finances, decreased fraud, and raised teacher and student satisfaction. The outcome of the previous study concurred with the findings of the current study.

CONCLUSION

The study found a constant relationship between administrative effectiveness and appropriate financial planning, transparency, and active engagement. Additionally, the bookkeeping procedures used by principals are essential to the efficient operation of secondary schools. Precise documentation promotes

responsibility, openness, and effective use of resources—all of which are essential for accomplishing learning objectives. Regular auditing is also essential for encouraging accountability, openness, and effectiveness in school management. It improves academic and administrative results, guarantees appropriate resource allocation, and cultivates trust among stakeholders.

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